

An Appraisal of Employment Status in India: A Spatio-Comparative Analysis of Social Groups

Dr. Sahab Deen Rawat,

Assistant Professor, School of Humanities, Lovely Professional University,
Phagwara, Punjab, E-mail: sahabdeenrawat@gmail.com

Abstract

The employment status of head of the household plays a significant role in shaping the prosperous life of the family members. Conventionally, India society is characterized by conspicuous dissimilarity among various social groups. Generally, Scheduled Castes (SC) described one of the most deprived social groups in term of occupation and employment in India, while Upper Castes (UC) having the privilege of occupational wealth in their life. The present research article focuses on appraisal employment status of head of the household for Upper Castes and Scheduled Castes in India. Present study is based on quantitative exercise of primary data collected from filed survey of eight states in India. A principal component analysis score has been calculated from different employment variables in order to analyse the spatial pattern of employment statuses of head of the household and plotted on the map by using Geographical Information System (GIS) technology. A analysis of employment status of head of the household for both social groups discloses that there is an enormous spatial inequality in the level of employment status across selected Indian states. However, the economic statuses of privileged castes are higher in comparison to underprivileged social group across India.

Keywords: *Employment Status, India, Upper-Castes (UC), Principal Component Analysis (PCA), Scheduled Castes (SC), Spatial Variation.*

Introduction

The employment status of head of the household plays an important role in the process of overall growth of the life of its members. Socioeconomic statuses of an individual have been embedded in the hierarchal social structure of Indian

society. The occupational nature and employment status of an individual is determined by their castes, class, gender religion and region across India. Indian society has been described as a “compartmentalized” society as it has a vast number of groups that maintain distinct and diverse styles of life. The system by which these groups are related and mutually accommodated is so complex as to defy general description (Galanter, 1984). There are several restricting traditional as well as customary practices prevails in in the society that direct the mode of occupational activities and employment in order to achieve an socioeconomic position in the Indian society. Consequently, various socioeconomic factors play a significant role in access to an occupation and economic activity based on labor divisions of the hierarchal structure of the society. Generally, skills and occupational aspirations of poor family is to be low because poor socio-economic background (Ganqgrade, 1974). Resultantly, Scheduled Castes socio-economic backgrounds of the Scheduled Castes are inferior in nature (Aikara, 1980). Most of the problems confronted by the Scheduled Castes have their origins in their prolonged backwardness and isolation due to their caste status. An underlying factor that makes these problems very prominent is their relatively poor background (Dreze, and Kingdon, 1999). Historically, lower castes and women have found at the bottom-level place in Indian society. The socio-economic backwardness of Scheduled Castes is the function of their traditionally lower position in the social hierarchy (Chauhan, 1975).

The present research paper is an attempt to appraise the employment status of head of the household foran advantaged group i.e. Upper-castes and disadvantaged group i.e. Scheduled Castes across India. The employment status of head of the household surveyed from both the social groups has been analyzed in terms of employment’s occupational activities in which head of the household is engaged in order their families’ economic life. The paper also presents an account of spatial variation in levels of employment status of head of

the household for both social groups across the surveyed regions. The present study can be divided into three major segments i.e. employment status, spatial analysis and discussion. The present article attempts to quantify the employment status of head of the household in order to present a Spatio-comparative analysis between privileged and underprivileged social groups.

Database and Research Methodology

The present research article is based on primary data collected from household surveys across the eight states of India. A total 603 samples had been interviewed with schedule of structured questionnaires from 40 villages of eight states in India. For appraisal of the employment status of head of the households for both social groups a composite index of five employment's variables i.e. casual labor, regular wage/ salaried, self-employed, retired/pension, public sector employee/executive post in private sectors, has been developed through the process of computation for Principal Component Analysis (PCA) score for the particular districts in order to analyze the spatial variation for Upper-Castes and Lower Castes across the surveyed states in India. The principal component analysis is the approach of index formation that offers a technique that synthesised a number of variables into one or few components or indicators. Thus, constructed index represents similar as possible with respect to all the variables/component characteristics that were synthesized into one or a few components (Abdi & Williams, 2010). Moreover, PCA is a multivariate technique for examining a data set in which observations are defined by several inter-correlated quantitative dependent variables. It combines a large number of variables into a few numbers of conceptual variables or component comprising the characteristics of all the combined variables (Jolliffe, 1986). Computer package SPSS 21 facilitates a calculation facility of Principal Component Analysis scores for a given distribution (NUEPA, 2009).

SL	PCA Index	Variables	KMO =0.6 Min.	BTS= p<0.0 5	CC = > 0.3 % & many	Eigen value = > 1	Scree Plot	Cmpnt. Explains	Cmpnt. Extracted	Rotation Solution
1	Scheduled Castes	5	0.258	0.000	Many	2	>1	39.141	First	Varimax
2	High Castes	5	0.133	0.000	Many	3	>1	36.457	First	Varimax

Source: Computed from Primary Data of Household Survey, 2015

To analysing and constructing PCA scores for the surveyed districts, total 603 household samples have been utilized to compute indices. The 40 location i.e. villages make 40 different cases across the surveyed districts in India. Thus, 40 cases (N=40) with the different number of variables for separate PCA index have been mention in Table 1. The essential characteristic of fulfilling the necessary conditions of Principal Component Analysis (PCA) scores for applying as index has been mentioned in the table 1.

Employment Status of Head of the Household

Parental employment and unemployment affect the level of social, cultural and economic capital available to individual and within family. Children’s socio-economic and educational achievement and outcomes are highly influenced by their parents’ employment pattern through the impact on children’s expectations and aspirations (Cusworth, 2016). Therefore, by increasing the improvement in the socio-economic status of workers the economic opportunity can be improved in order to reduce inequality (Bernanke, 2008). For the assessment of employment status of head of the household a composite index (Head of the Household Employment Index-HHEI) has been used to show the spatial pattern between Upper-Castes and Lower Castes (SCs) in the study area.

Scheduled Castes

Employment status of head of the household of Scheduled Castes family shows that 53% head of the family were engaged in daily wage casual labor and 9% were working with regular wage or salaried employee in private sector. Another, 11% of the head of the households was self-employed and 5% were retired/pensioner form government sector. Remaining 9% of the total head of the households were working either in government sector or at the post of excusive employee in a private sector (appendix-1).

Source: Computed from Primary Data of Household Survey, 2015

Spatial distribution of employment status of head of the household of Scheduled Castes family reveals that the district Ajmer has recorded highest HHEI score with 2.11 followed by Sonbhadra and Bikaner. On the r hand, district SPS Nellore (-1.45) records lowest level of employment status proceeded by Mallapuram and Kolhapur. The map 1 show that the Scheduled Casteshhead of the families is

relatively better in the districts of Northern states than the Southern states especially in Rajasthan.

In the northern states, total 7 districts Udaipur, Mathura and Murshidabad etc. recodes high level, 5 districts like Barmer, Bijnor and Araria etc. register medium level and, 8 districts like Alwar, Sitapur and Banka etc. recorded low level employment status for Scheduled Castes' head of the family. Regarding Southern states, only Davanagere recorded high level; 7 districts like Nagpur, Mysore and Kannur etc. show medium level employment status of Scheduled Castes' head of the household. Remaining 10 districts like Aurangabad, Karwar and Anantapur etc. have recorded low level of employment status for scheduled castes head of the family (Map-1).

Upper Castes (Non-Reserved)

Employment status of head of the household of Upper-Castes' families indicate that 2% head of the families were engaged in daily wage casual labor, and 8% were working with regular wage or salaried employed in private sector. Major section of 45% heads of the households was self-employed and 16% were retired from government job or pensioner. Another major and important segment of 19% heads of the households were found working either in government sector or at the post of exclusive employee in a private sector (appendix-2).

District level pattern of employment status of head of the household of Upper-Castes' families suggest that the district Ernakulam has recorded highest HHEI score with 1.81 followed by Mallapuram and Kannur. On the other hand, district Davanagere (-1.58) registers at bottom level employment status preceded by Nalgonda and Aurangabad. The map 2 display that the Upper-Castes' head of the families having relatively better employment status in the districts of Northern states in comparison to Southern states. On the subject of Northern states, total 6 districts Bikaner, Sitapur, West Midnapore etc. have recoded high level of

employment status of head the families, and 13 districts like Ajmer, Gorakhpur and Rohtas etc. have registered medium level for the Upper Castes. There is only one district of Bijnor show the low level of employment status of Upper-Castes' head of the family. There were total 6 districts of Southern states like Bengaluru Rural, Kannur and Mallapuram etc. recoded high level employment status of head the families; and 5 districts like Pune, Karwar etc. show medium level employment status of head the families. Remaining 9 districts like Kolhapur, Nalgonda and Davanagere etc. registered low level of employment status for Upper-Castes' head of the families.

Discussion

Spatial analysis of employment status of head the Scheduled Castes household reveals that majority (53%) of the Scheduled Castes head of the family were engaged in daily wage casual labour work. Furthermore, 34% head the Scheduled Castes' households were engaged in non-daily wage casual labour i.e. regular wages, self employed, retired or pensioner; and only 9% of head the Scheduled Castes' households were in government sectors or executive employee in private sector. On the Contrary, majority (88%) of Upper-Castes' head of the households were working in regular works i.e. regular wages, self employed, retired or pensioner. There was 19% Upper-Castes' head of the households found working in government sectors or executive employee in private sector; whereas only 2% Upper-Castes' head of the households were engaged in daily wage casual labourer works. In case of availability of regular works i.e. regular wage/salaried and retired or pensioner Upper-Castes' head of the households are in better position in comparison to Scheduled Castes. Thus, overall Upper-Castes' head of the households are in better and superior position of employment in comparison to Scheduled Castes head of the households across the study area. As per the order of social hierarchy, Schedule Castes suffer at the

lower strata where material deprivation and impurity reinforce one another (Beteille, 1998).

The comparative investigation of Map 1 and Map 2 reveals that the districts of Northern states are relatively better than Southern states in employment statuses of head of the households for both the social groups with little exception. However, Kerala, Uttar Pradesh, Rajasthan, Bihar and West Bengal are best in employment status of for Upper-castes' head of the families. On the other hand, Rajasthan has recorded highest position in comparison to remaining states for employment status of Upper-Castes' head of the families.

The above discussion divulges that both the social groups in Northern states are relatively better than Southern states in employment status of head of Households. On the contrary, Northern states are far better than Southern states in the levels of employment status of Scheduled Castes' head of families especially in Rajasthan. The employment statuses of Upper-Castes' head of the families in all the surveyed Northern states along with Kerala have recorded higher position in comparison to remaining states in the study area.

The careful discussion of the above has reveals three notable point: 1) overall employment status of Upper-Castes' head of the families are in better position in comparison to Scheduled Castes, 2) generally employment of head of the both social groups in northern states having better position in comparison to Southern states, 3) the employment status of Upper-Castes 'head of the families are good in Northern states along with Kerala. Thus, we can state that the Scheduled Castes have lesser possibility to grow and achieve the successful life in comparison to Upper-Castes population. As stated the reason for the continued backwardness among SCs is poverty, inaccessibility, wastage of old age practice and tradition prevailing in the society (Aikara, 1996). Since, Scheduled Castes across the surveyed regions having a lower possibility to enhance their social

and economic status because socio-economic deprivation an individual accumulates less human capital due to their much cost-sensitiveness (Declercq and Verboven, 2015).

Conclusion

The painstaking analysis of employment status of head of households reveals that level of employment status of head of the families suffers from spatial variation for both the social groups across India. However, Northern states record comparatively better employment status of head of the families for both the social groups. The comparative analysis of employment status of head of the family between Upper-Castes and Lower Castes (Scheduled Castes) show that Upper-Castes' head of the families having relatively higher status in comparison to Scheduled Castes (Appendix-1 & 2). The Scheduled Castes is considered one of the most underprivileged sections of Indian society that has been evidently verified true in the light of PCA score based on primary data in terms of Spatio-comparative analysis of employment status of head of households between Upper-Castes and Scheduled Castes across India. Customarily, Upper-Castes' family heads are far better in position of employment status. Most of them are engagement in secondary and tertiary economic occupation; while mostly Scheduled Castes' are engaged in primary economic activities such as daily wage casual labourers and marginal workers which brought them lower economic status. Therefore, the social and economic conditions of Scheduled Castes remain as backwards and most of them are still engaged in low income-generating occupations like daily wage labourers and other menial works (Sinha, 1981).

References

- Abdi, H. & Williams, L.J. (2010). Principal Component Analysis. Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews: Computational Statistics. 2 (4): 433–459.
- Aikara, J. (1980). Scheduled castes and Higher Education: A Study of College Students in Mumbai. Pune, Ramchandra Dastane.

Aikara, Jacob (1996). Inequality of Educational Opportunities: The Case of SCs in India. *Journal of Educational Planning and Administration*, Vol. X, No.1, January 1996, pp. 1-14.

Ben Bernanke, Harvard Class Day 2008.

Beteille, Andre, (1998). *Pollution and Poverty*. in J. Michael Mahar (ed) *The Untouchables of Contemporary India*, New Delhi; Rawat Publication.

Chauhan, B.R. (1975). Special problems of Scheduled Castes. in M. S. Gore, et al. (ed.), *Papers in the Sociology of Education in India*, Delhi, NCERT.

Dreze, J. and G.G. Kingdon (1999). *School Participation in Rural India*. LSE Development Economics Discussion Paper Series, No.18, London: London School of Economics.

Galanter, M. (1984). *Competing Inequalities: Law and the Backward Classes in India*. Berkely, California University Press.

Ganqgrade, K.D. (1974). *Educational Problems of Scheduled Castes in Haryana (college students)*. Delhi School of Social Work.

Jolliffe I.T. (1986). *Principal Component Analysis and Factor Analysis*. In: *Principal Component Analysis*. Springer Series in Statistics. Springer, New York, NY.

Koen Declercq and Frank Verboven (2015), 'Socio-economic status and participation in higher education: Do costs matter?', *Education Economics*, 2015 (Sept 2014), 23(5), 532-556.

Linda Cusworth, (2016 book). *The Impact of parental Employment: Young people, Well Being, and Educational Achievement*. University of York, Routledge Taylor & Francis group, New York.

NUEPA (2009). *Educational Development Index (EDI): a Suggestive Framework for Computation*. Department of Educational Management Information System, NUEPA, Version 2: 2009.

Sinha, S. 1981). *Level of educational development among the Scheduled castes of Bihar*. unpublished Dissertation, CSRD, SSS, Jawaharlal Nehru University.

Appendix

Appendix-1							
Employment Status of Head of the Household of Scheduled Castes							
SL	District	Casual Labor	Regular Wage/ Salaried	Self-Employed	Retired/ Pension	Public/ Executive Job	Head Household Employment Index (HHEI)
1	Ernakulam	45.45	9.09	9.09	9.09	9.09	0.022
2	Thiruvananthapuram	70.00	0.00	20.00	0.00	0.00	-0.286
3	Alappuzha	54.55	0.00	18.18	0.00	9.09	0.319
4	Mallapuram	80.00	10.00	0.00	10.00	0.00	-1.393
5	Kannur	40.00	10.00	10.00	20.00	10.00	0.093
6	Mysore	80.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	10.00	-0.848
7	Bengaluru Rural	50.00	0.00	30.00	0.00	10.00	0.905
8	Uttara Kannada	40.00	0.00	0.00	20.00	0.00	-0.669
9	Davanagere	50.00	0.00	30.00	0.00	20.00	1.316
10	Kalburagi	40.00	10.00	10.00	20.00	10.00	0.093
11	Anantapur	80.00	10.00	10.00	0.00	0.00	-0.908
12	SPS Nellore	90.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	-1.454
13	Visakhapatnam	40.00	40.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	-0.628
14	Nalgonda	40.00	10.00	0.00	0.00	30.00	0.719
15	Karimnagar	70.00	10.00	0.00	10.00	0.00	-1.197
16	Nagpur	30.00	30.00	0.00	0.00	10.00	0.017
17	Latur	70.00	10.00	10.00	0.00	0.00	-0.712
18	Kolhapur	80.00	10.00	0.00	10.00	0.00	-1.393
19	Pune	60.00	10.00	0.00	10.00	20.00	-0.180
20	Aurangabad	60.00	10.00	10.00	0.00	0.00	-0.517
21	Udaipur	20.00	10.00	40.00	20.00	10.00	1.650
22	Barmer	50.00	10.00	10.00	0.00	10.00	0.090
23	Bikaner	30.00	10.00	20.00	0.00	30.00	1.692
24	Ajmer	30.00	0.00	30.00	0.00	30.00	2.118
25	Alwar	70.00	0.00	0.00	10.00	10.00	-0.749
26	Purulia	60.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	10.00	-0.457
27	W. Midnapore	80.00	0.00	10.00	0.00	10.00	-0.459
28	S.24 Parganas	10.00	20.00	20.00	0.00	10.00	1.223
29	Murshidabad	40.00	0.00	40.00	0.00	0.00	1.078
30	Jalpaiguri	70.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	10.00	-0.652
31	Araria	50.00	10.00	10.00	0.00	10.00	0.090
32	Banka	80.00	10.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	-1.297
33	Samastipur	50.00	20.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	-0.748
34	W. Champaran	20.00	20.00	10.00	20.00	20.00	0.857
35	Rohtas	70.00	10.00	0.00	10.00	0.00	-1.197
36	Gorakhpur	50.00	0.00	0.00	10.00	20.00	0.054
37	Sonbhadra	18.18	27.27	18.18	0.00	36.36	2.048
38	Sitapur	80.00	0.00	10.00	0.00	0.00	-0.870
39	Bijnor	50.00	10.00	30.00	0.00	10.00	0.867
40	Mathura	20.00	10.00	30.00	10.00	10.00	1.358
	Total	52.85	8.68	10.92	4.71	9.43	0.006

Source: Computed from Primary Data of Household Survey, 2015

Appendix-2							
Employment Status of Head of the Household of Non-Reserved Castes							
SL	District	Casual Labor	Regular Wage/ Salaried	Self-Employed	Retired/ Pension	Public/ Executive Job	Head Household Employment Index (HHEI)
1	Ernakulam	0.00	0.00	0.00	20.00	80.00	1.809
2	Thiruvananthapuram	40.00	0.00	40.00	0.00	20.00	0.172
3	Alappuzha	0.00	0.00	0.00	60.00	0.00	0.712
4	Mallapuram	0.00	0.00	0.00	20.00	80.00	1.809
5	Kannur	0.00	20.00	0.00	40.00	40.00	1.555
6	Mysore	0.00	40.00	0.00	0.00	40.00	1.465
7	Bengaluru Rural	0.00	0.00	0.00	60.00	20.00	1.082
8	Uttara Kannada	0.00	0.00	60.00	20.00	20.00	-0.331
9	Davanagere	0.00	0.00	100.00	0.00	0.00	-1.579
10	Kalburagi	0.00	20.00	60.00	0.00	0.00	-1.044
11	Anantapur	0.00	0.00	80.00	20.00	0.00	-0.599
12	SPS Nellore	0.00	0.00	60.00	20.00	0.00	-0.701
13	Visakhapatnam	0.00	20.00	80.00	0.00	0.00	-0.942
14	Nalgonda	0.00	0.00	100.00	0.00	0.00	-1.579
15	Karimnagar	0.00	20.00	80.00	0.00	0.00	-0.942
16	Nagpur	0.00	20.00	80.00	0.00	0.00	-0.942
17	Latur	0.00	20.00	80.00	0.00	0.00	-0.942
18	Kolhapur	0.00	0.00	80.00	0.00	0.00	-1.236
19	Pune	0.00	0.00	60.00	20.00	20.00	-0.331
20	Aurangabad	0.00	0.00	100.00	0.00	0.00	-1.579
21	Udaipur	0.00	0.00	60.00	20.00	0.00	-0.701
22	Barmer	0.00	0.00	40.00	20.00	20.00	0.012
23	Bikaner	0.00	0.00	20.00	60.00	20.00	0.739
24	Ajmer	0.00	40.00	20.00	20.00	0.00	0.573
25	Alwar	0.00	0.00	20.00	0.00	80.00	1.273
26	Purulia	0.00	20.00	0.00	0.00	40.00	1.170
27	W. Midnapore	0.00	20.00	60.00	0.00	20.00	-0.229
28	S.24 Parganas	0.00	20.00	60.00	0.00	0.00	-0.599
29	Murshidabad	0.00	0.00	20.00	0.00	80.00	1.273
30	Jalpaiguri	20.00	0.00	20.00	20.00	20.00	0.531
31	Araria	0.00	20.00	20.00	40.00	0.00	0.471
32	Banka	0.00	0.00	60.00	20.00	0.00	-0.701
33	Samastipur	20.00	20.00	20.00	20.00	0.00	0.455
34	W. Champaran	0.00	0.00	60.00	20.00	20.00	-0.331
35	Rohtas	0.00	0.00	40.00	20.00	20.00	0.012
36	Gorakhpur	0.00	0.00	40.00	20.00	40.00	0.382
37	Sonbhadra	0.00	0.00	0.00	60.00	20.00	1.082
38	Sitapur	0.00	20.00	20.00	0.00	40.00	0.827
39	Bijnor	0.00	0.00	100.00	0.00	0.00	-1.579
40	Mathura	0.00	0.00	60.00	0.00	20.00	-0.523
	Total	2.00	8.00	45.00	15.50	19.00	0.000

Source: Computed from Primary Data of Household Survey, 2015